

THE SEMANTIC IN NOUN PHRASES

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Abstract. In this article significant branch of lexicology "semantic" is learned and the semantic in noun phrases is analyzed. Furthermore, some examples are given which had been examined and explained by famous scientists and learners.

Key words: semantic, semantic relation, semantic role, NP (noun phrases).

СЕМАНТИКА ИМЕННЫХ ФРАЗ

Аннотация. В данной статье изучается значимая отрасль лексикологии «семантическая» и анализируется семантика в именных словосочетаниях. Кроме того, приведены некоторые примеры, которые были рассмотрены и объяснены известными учеными и учениками.

Ключевые слова: семантика, смысловое отношение, смысловая роль, НП (именные словосочетания).

As you know the branch of lexicology that studies word meaning is called semantics. One of the major characteristics of the word is the ability to accept different grammatical forms and convey grammatical meaning in speech. Having considered the main characteristics of the word, we can proceed to its definition. A word is a speech unit used for communication between people, which has a material representation in the form of a group of sounds, a meaning, and is characterized by both formal and semantic unity. Following these ideas, semantics are semantic relations in a sentence, context or speech. " The semantic relations are the underlying relations between two concepts expressed by words or phrases. We distinguish here between semantic relations and semantic roles. Semantic roles are always between verbs (or nouns derived from verbs) and other constituents (run quickly, went to the store, computer maker), whereas semantic relations can occur between any constituents, for example in complex nominals (malaria mosquito (CAUSE)), genitives (girl's mouth (PART-WHOLE)), prepositional phrases attached to nouns (man at the store (LOCATIVE)), or discourse level (The bus was late. As a result, I missed my appointment (CAUSE)). Thus, in a sense, semantic relations are more general than semantic roles and many semantic role types will appear on our list of semantic relations. The following NP level constructions are considered here (cf. the classifications provided by (Quirket al.1985) and (Semmelmeyer and Bolander 1992)):

(1) Compound Nominals consisting of two consecutive nouns (eg night club - a TEMPORAL relation - indicating that club functions at night),

(2) Adjective Noun constructions where the adjectival modifier is derived from a noun (eg musical clock - a MAKE/PRODUCE relation),

(3) Genitives (eg the door of the car - a PART-WHOLE relation), and

(4) Adjective phrases (cf. (Semmelmeyer and Bolander 1992)) in which the modifier noun is expressed by a prepositional phrase which functions as an adjective(eg toy in the box - a LOCATION relation)." [1]

Here we can see some examples for the semantic roles for noun phrases:

Agent- An animate being deliberately performing an action

Theme- Similar to patients - theme moves from one location to another.

Recipient- an animate entity that is the beneficiary of an action. introduced by to.

Experiencer- an animate being that experiences a feeling

Stimulus- something that causes an experience

Patient- Similar to theme - is physically affected by the verb's action

Goal- like a recipient that does not benefit from the action, introduced by to.

Instrument- The cause of a verb's action, not volitional unlike agent.

"According Chierchia's analysis of noun phrases across languages is based on the concept of semantic type. Under this framework, the fundamental types are truth values and entities. Montague's notation uses the letter e to denote an entity and t to denote a truth value (Chierchia 342, note 4). A truth value is the type of a complete proposition, or a declarative sentence. For example, the sentence It is raining outside has a truth value, either true or false. An entity represents a specific individual in a world (either the real world or a hypothetical world). For example, my pen denotes a specific object in the real world. Other examples of entities in English are my teapots (a plural entity), tea (a mass entity) and delight (an abstract entity). Entities can appear in argument positions in a sentence." [2]

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